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The Role of Information Technologies in the Innovative Development of Banks

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Abstract

Improvement of information technologies, as well as their widespread use as a key factor in the innovative development of banking, as in all areas, is one of the most pressing issues. This article reveals the role of information technology in the innovative development of banks. The role of modern information technologies as a means of competition in the market of remote banking services and banking services is widely analyzed. International experience on risks and security measures in the provision of modern banking services is studied and methods of risk management are described. In addition, statistical analysis was conducted on modern technologies introduced in the country. Also, proposals for further innovative development of banks on the basis of modern information technologies have been developed.

Keywords: banking, information, technology, deposit, credit, virtual banking, online banking, mobile banking, digital banking.

Introduction

The development of modern information technologies is the basis for the further development of the activities of the industries based on the automation of the work of the industries, the reduction of the participation of the human factor, the transition of the traditional processes to the virtual appearance and the integration of various practices.

In the conditions of today's globalization, the need for digital information and communication technologies, which are the achievements of technological development in all areas, is being shown. Because technological modernization leads to cost reduction, quality improvement, reduction of excessive time consumption in every field, in other words, to achieve high efficiency. It can be said that all these have developed rapidly since the second half of the 20th century and have covered almost all areas by today's time. Of course, the banking sector should be recognized as one of these sectors.

It is worth noting that effective use of digital information technologies and innovative organization of work based on them will further develop banks, increase the investment attractiveness of the banking institution and have a positive effect on its capitalization.

However, further increasing the level of capitalization of banks - to achieve this by injecting additional capital, expanding the deposit base, increasing the volume of loans directed to the economy with high profits and optimizing banking activities - is typical of the activities of traditional banks.

The world experience and banking practices achieved in the banking system of our country show that in order to further develop the activity of banks, it is necessary to introduce new forms of banking products and services based on modern information technologies and increase their quality, to withstand competition in the market of banking services, as well as to achieve stable operation in this environment. possible

Of course, it also depends on the banks' solvency and other capabilities. However, in today's competitive market, one of the urgent issues is the updating of modern technological and software supplies, not only for efficient operation, but also for stable operation.

In the ever improving market of banking services, the growing demand for remote banking services, which are different from traditional banking services, requires banks to solve a number of tasks. In particular, it is necessary to organize services such as "Virtual banking", "Online banking", "Mobile banking" in a high-quality and wide-ranging, at the same time simple and understandable form, and to regularly improve them.

This requires banks to develop and quickly implement their innovation strategy, taking into account political, economic, organizational and other aspects.

In general, the main goal of the development of information technologies is to create a modern information technology structure that can improve the activities of industries and ensure their sustainable development. This is especially important for the banking system. Because incomparable competitive advantages in the activity of banks, that is, the main strategic tasks can be performed precisely through information technologies.

Information technology is important because it serves to solve the problems related to banks facing the new economy. Information technology is the basis of recent reforms in the financial sector aimed at increasing the speed and reliability of financial transactions and initiatives to strengthen the banking sector.

After all, the activity of banks cannot be imagined without information and communication technologies.

It can also be seen from the world practice that the information technology revolution has created an unprecedented growth of financial activity all over the world. Advances in technology and the development of networks around the world have significantly reduced the cost of global money transfers/

It also led to the integration of information exchange processes between networks and sectors. This made it possible to remotely organize the activities of many networks.

In particular, it allows the banking sector to go beyond traditional activities and is now determining the main directions of activity. Instead, the demands of bank customers have increased, and now they have become more demanding. Because they have more technical knowledge compared to the previous era. They demand the ability to use any banking services quickly, anywhere and anytime.

Therefore, information and communication technologies have become an important component of the development strategy of banks aimed at improving any banking services. After all, information technologies are the main element in the use of intellectual capital and the improvement of the efficiency of innovation processes in the banking sector. In other words, information technology is having a major impact on the reshaping of the banking industry, leading to the creation of new financial products and new means of their delivery.

In general, another reason for innovation is change, the main focus of many banks and financial institutions to cope with the change, which is not only rapid, but also complex, and to gain a place in the competitive market is the digitization of banking services. Behind all this lies the Internet and modern information technologies.

In recent years, many successful banks have been competing to win customer trust by introducing advanced technologies into the service industry. This allows them to additionally reduce costs and obtain higher profits. Of course, innovations in the field of information technologies, that is, most of the projects of innovative information technologies fall on the banking sector, because banks are engaged in remote services and they cannot do without information technologies. Technological innovation allows competing banks not only to successfully compete for customers, but also to significantly modernize the nature and methods of customer interaction. Such technologies, first of all, create wide opportunities for the organization of various forms of remote banking services. It will also increase competition within the industry and make life simpler and easier due to the automation of many banking operations.

Compared to other industries, financial institutions are increasingly required to collect, process and analyze data to meet customer needs. Therefore, banks were the first to introduce automated information processing technology. It should also be noted that there are three reasons why financial institutions have invested heavily in technology so far:

First, to achieve a reduction in operating costs;

Second, by offering new banking products and services while increasing the convenience and value of existing products and services, serving its customers, as well as attracting new customers;

The third is to be able to introduce risk and information management systems and methods with the help of new technologies.

Advances in information technology have made it possible for banks and other financial institutions to provide a range of products and services to their retail and wholesale customers at the click of a mouse. This type of bank is mainly called "Electronic banking". The development of "Electronic banking" brings benefits as well as costs. In other words, "Electronic banking" has changed the traditional risks and benefits associated with banking. Therefore, it can be said that the overall risks of banks have increased. This increase in the scope of risk can be explained by the speed of changes, technological progress and the global character of open electronic networks, the integration of the electronic banking system into the

computer system, and the dependence of banks on third parties in the provision of information technology. However, the positive aspects of this stage of development can be described as follows: a larger customer base, lower costs and higher profits.

According to studies, protection of identity information is one of the main criteria for the effective operation of the bank. Therefore, financial institutions are using biometric parameters to identify employees. These include, for example, security systems such as fingerprints and eye scanners.

As a result, the confidence of customers in the bank increases and has a positive effect on the popularity of banking services.

The banking environment today has become highly competitive. In order to be able to survive and grow in the changing market conditions, banks are using the fastest technologies, which are seen as a means of reducing costs and effective communication with people and institutions related to banking business.

The processes of using modern information technologies and the elimination of risks arising from the use of banking products and services provided on the basis of them, and protection against malicious attacks are one of the most important problems. Especially, this is one of the important directions in banking practice. Therefore, advanced banks are using a biometric protection system instead of the traditional "password and password" form of protection.

In this regard, according to the research results of the Gartner group, the costs of the security system, the composition of the problems and the advantages of the biometric security system have been determined as follows:

- every year, companies spend 150-200 USD to manage passwords for employee accounts;
- 60% of support requests consist of account problems due to the fact that the employee forgot their password or blocked their account information;
- a quarter of employees store passwords in text files on their desktops.

Therefore, biometrics not only improves security, but also reduces the cost of storing employee passwords.

According to the analysis, the main purpose of using information technology systems in banks is data protection. Another system used to protect information is identification of employees using biometric data. About 80 percent of basic hackers do their work using misused usernames and passwords (Computer Emergency Response Team), more than 70 percent of security breaches involve bank employees (CSI/FBI Computer Crime Survey), and about 75 percent of employee personal information discloses to colleagues (SecurEnvoy).

In recent years, as a result of the reforms carried out in the banking system in our country, the weight of banking products and services has increased in the services market, and their forms, in particular, remote banking services, are being formed and improved.

According to the information of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of commercial banks operating in our republic increased by 2 during 2020, and their total number reached 32 as of January 1 of this year. 13 of them are banks with a high share of state capital, 14 are banks with a high share of private capital, and 5 are banks with a high share of foreign banks in their capital.

In particular, as part of the measures to expand the participation of foreign investors in the banking system, the joint-stock commercial bank "Tenge" established in Tashkent by Khaliq Bank, a large bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan, has started its operation, while the first digital bank in our country, that is, "ANOR BANK" JSC, is a commercial digital bank. banking activity has been launched.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Currently, the number of branches of commercial banks is 861, the number of banking service centers (service offices and ATMs) is 1,222, and the number of 24/7 branch offices is 1,452, through which appropriate banking services are provided to customers [15].

As of January 1, 2021, the number of users of these banking services is about 14.6 million. making up 4.4 mln. compared to the corresponding period of the previous year. increased to Of these, 822.5 thousand or 5.6 percent are legal entities and individual entrepreneurs, and 13,748.6 thousand or 94.4 percent are individuals.

In our opinion, increasing the role of modern information technologies in the further development of banks' activities and developing promising strategies for improving banks' activities based on this, it is appropriate to take into account the following:

1. Reviewing directions for increasing financial popularity in cooperation with the World Bank and other international banks and developing measures to be implemented;
2. Privatization of state-owned banks and thereby creating conditions for the formation of healthy competition in the market of banking services;
3. Wide introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the activity of banks in order to improve the system of providing high-quality and fast banking services;
4. Improving the qualifications of bank employees and the ability to work with modern information technologies, as well as the appropriate promotion of qualified specialists;
5. It is necessary to eliminate technical failures in the process of providing remote banking services and to organize the use of high-capacity communication servers.

In conclusion, it can be said that the modernization of banks' activities on the basis of modern information and communication technologies makes it possible to bring the activities of banks to a new stage in terms of quality and modern requirements. Because, in the conditions of increasingly developing digital economy, it is information technologies that are the main factor of ensuring strong competitiveness in the market of banking services. Of course, on the other hand, we should not forget the contribution of creatively thinking qualified specialists working in the field.

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